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—
The Common Good 2.0:
System Genesis

Conference Paper Extract
Practice-Led Research

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IN/DI/VISIBLE
Social Responsibility in the Age of
Entropocene

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Tischner University, Krakow, Poland
31 March 2023

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This foundational baseline establishes the "exponential decline of the commons" and probes universal education and participatory democracy as systemic solutions. As the opening extract in the sequence, it sits in visible contrast to the plainer analytical register of the later working papers (2026). The Visual Rhetoric extract documents the transition from emotive practitioner methodology to the more structured framing that follows.

Cluster 01: The Diachronic Evolution of Capital.

P.3–7 / A sequential mapping tracking the transition from Nomadic social structures to post-1980s Neo-Feudalism and Hyper-Capitalism.

Cluster 02: Comparative Democratic Architectures.

P.8–10 / An analysis contrasting Representative, Direct, and Deliberative models of citizen participation.

Cluster 03: The Dynamics of Problem Solving.

P.11–13 / Defining the cognitive friction between identifying the macro-problem and navigating toward a workable solution.

Cluster 04: The Cognitive Funnel.

P.14–16 / The application of the Double Diamond methodology (Discover, Define, Develop, Deliver) to civic complexity.

Cluster 05: The Epistemological Requirement.

P.17 / A taxonomy of 'Futureproof' educational literacies necessary for civic participation (including Applied Creativity and Computational Thinking).

Cluster 06: The Common Good 2.0 Macro-Scaffold.

P.18–19 / The four-part architecture required for systemic intervention: Education, Citizen Designers, New Democracy, and Systems Change.

Cluster 07: The Participatory Collective.

P. 20) / An intersectional diagram mapping the 'Citizen Community' as the central node connecting disparate domains (Finance, Law, Ecology).

Balance
Capital

—
Pre-History

*Social
Capital*

NOMADIC

—
Family
Tribal

Community
Cooperation

*Wealth
Capital*

Balance
Capital

—
Pre-Modern

FUEDAL

—
Lords
Serfs
Famine
Disease

Wealth
Capital

Social
Capital

Balance
Capital

—
Post WWII
Cooperation
Solidarity

GLOBAL EMERGENCY

—

United Nations
European Project
Welfare States

Social
Capital

World Health Organisation

Wealth
Capital

Balance
Capital

—
1980s
Neo-Liberaism
De-Regulation
~~Communism~~

INDIVIDUAL

—
“There’s no such
thing as society”
Thatcher
UK PM

Wealth
Capital

Social
Capital

Balance
Capitalism

—
2023
Neo-Fuedalism

NEO-FUEDAL

—
1%

Hyper-Capitalism
Social Deline
Environmental Catastrophe

Wealth
Capital

Social
Capital

Money

Systems
Extractive Wealth
Exceptionalism

Shareholders

Banking

Markets

Fossil

Technology

Industry

The Commons
Citizens
Community
Society
Ecology
Planet

Democracy

Representative Democracy

Direct Democracy

Deliberative Democracy

Citizen

—

Passive

Delegates

Election

Not responsible

Min. Time

Min. Engagement

Politician

—

Mandated Power

Defined period

Responsible

Makes decisions

Accountable

Democracy

Representative Democracy

Direct Democracy

Deliberative Democracy

Citizen

—

Pro-active

Responsible

Invest Time

Dialogue

Engagement

Participation

Referenda

Politician

—

Facilitates

Formulates

Implements

Democracy

Representative Democracy

Direct Democracy

Deliberative Democracy

Citizen

—

Deliberative

Informed Assembly

Referenda

Dialogue

Engagement

Participation

Min. Time

Politician

—

Assembly Led

Limited Mandate

Facilitates

Formulates

Implements

Defined period

Design Method

Democracy

**Citizen
Assemblies
Ireland**

1. Ass

96

Platform

Time

Space

Information

Dialogue

Capacity

No

No Safe

No Self-Preservation

3 X Rs

01. Reading

02. Writing

03. Arithmetic

4 X Cs

01. Applied Creativity

02. Critical Thinking

03. Communication

04. Collaboration

7 X Cs + 3 X Rs 2.0

01. Applied Creativity

02. Critical Thinking

03. Communication

04. Collaboration

05. Computational

06. Cross Cultural

07. Career Learning

01. Resilience

02. Reflection

03. Relationships

Education

Core Literacies

Futureproof

Common Good 2.0

Radical Change

Scaffolding for
Collective Action

INCOMPLETE MANIFESTO

Common Good 2.0

Radical Change

Scaffolding for

Collective Action

01. EDUCATE SUPER CITIZENS
02. BUILD PLATFORMS + STRUCTURES
03. NEW PARTICIPATORY DEMOCRACY
04. WISDOM OF (INFORMED) CROWDS
05. TO PROBLEM-SOLVE COLLECTIVELY
06. OPEN SOURCE SYSTEMS CHANGE
07. AMPLIFY + ACCELERATE
TIPPING POINTS

03. New
Democracy

Common Interest
Ground-Up.
Top-Down
Outside-In.
Inside-Out

04.
Systems
Change

Design

Participatory

Collective

